

**DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE CONCEPTS “CONCEPT” AND
“WORD”. MEANS OF OBJECTIVIZATION OF THE CONCEPT IN
RUSSIAN LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the conceptual range of the terms “*concept*” and “*word*”, which are closely interconnected and constantly interact in modern linguistics. The article explores the issue of differentiating between the two terms — “*concept*” and “*word*.” In this regard, attention is focused on various scientific viewpoints regarding their distinction. An attempt is also made to identify the distinctive features of “*concept*” and “*word*” based on the works of many researchers. The study reveals that there exists a certain differentiation between these terms.

Keywords: concept, word, meaning, world, association, knowledge, lexeme, semantics, linguistics, conceptology, lexical meaning, conceptual features, conceptual structure, cognitive consciousness of the individual.

INTRODUCTION

The term “*concept*” is one of the most controversial in cognitive linguistics, although its study began approximately in the 1920s–1930s. Many domestic scholars have studied the problem of the concept, among them E.S. Kubryakova, V.A. Maslova, I.A. Sternin, V.I. Karasik, and Z.D. Popova. Linguists note that the concept has a multifaceted nature, which makes its study more complex. The *concept* represents a complex, global phenomenon connected with the individual’s mental activity aimed at categorizing various objects. Certain factors influence the understanding of a concept: the cultural aspect, experience, knowledge, nationality, mentality, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Since the concept is objectified through language, and the word that objectifies it obtains the status of its name, modern conceptology raises an important problem — the relationship between the notions *concept* and *word*, or more precisely, its lexical meaning. According to R. Jackendoff, the meanings of linguistic units are equivalent to the concepts or conceptual structures they express. This view equates meanings with concepts; however, such identification is deemed unacceptable, since “concepts, as elements of consciousness, are quite autonomous from language” [2, p. 26–27].

D.S. Likhachev believed that “the concept exists not for the word itself, but for each main (dictionary) meaning of the word separately” [5, p. 282]. The material is analyzed using a comparative method. N.N. Boldyrev points out that people often master words not at the level of their meanings, but at the level of the senses they convey — i.e., concepts and conceptual meanings. They use words as ready-made clichés (similar to grammatical forms) in completely different contexts without considering the meaning attached to these words in the minds of most people, which serves as a basis for understanding. As an illustration, the researcher cites some politicians’ statements: “I don’t dig the ground among deputies” or “My head is far from thought.” Violations of phraseological collocation in these expressions convey an entirely different sense than intended [2, p. 26–27].

However, not all concepts existing in human consciousness can be represented in language. For example, Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin note the concept of “*zero food*” exists in consciousness but is not expressed in a word — we understand that such food exists, but it is not real food [6, p. 24].

The lexical meaning reflects the core sense or the denotative meaning of a word and constitutes one of the key aspects of its semantics. It represents the sense or concept linked with a particular word. When we use a word, we ascribe to it a certain lexical meaning corresponding to a notion or idea. Thus, the lexical meaning

of a word is related to the concept but can be subject to interpretation and contextual variation.

Lexical meaning, defined in dictionaries, is based on generally accepted notions. However, each individual may have their own interpretation based on personal experience, knowledge, and context. Therefore, even though the lexical meaning correlates with the general concept, it may differ slightly across individuals.

According to N.N. Boldyrev, “the meaning of a word is only an attempt to give a general representation of the content of the expressed concept, to outline its known boundaries and to present some of its features through a given word” [2, p. 27]. Although lexical meaning corresponds to the concept, it is not identical to it, encompassing numerous connotations (evaluative, ideological, cultural, etc.) and associations fixed in linguistic consciousness. Even within this broader approach, lexical meaning remains narrower than the concept [8, p. 484].

RESULTS

A *concept* is understood as a basic cognitive unit representing an abstract notion of something or someone. Concepts help classify the surrounding world and organize our knowledge. *Words*, on the other hand, are linguistic symbols used to express and convey concepts. They serve as sound or written forms associated with specific meanings.

The relationship between concepts and words lies in the fact that words denote concepts. When we use a word, we evoke the corresponding concept — an abstract representation of what the word denotes. However, the link between words and concepts is not always straightforward: one word can correspond to several concepts, and one concept can be represented by several words. Moreover, different languages may vary in how certain concepts are expressed.

DISCUSSION

Drawing a line between *concept* and *word*, Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin note

that “the psychophysiological basis of a concept is a certain sensory image to which the knowledge about the world is ‘attached,’ forming the content of the concept. In a word, however, two components are distinguished: the sound component — the signifier (lexeme) and the semantic component — the signified (sememe)” [6, p. 17].

Concepts reflect our understanding of the world, while words are tools we use to communicate and share this understanding. Words are linguistic shells for concepts that make them usable in communication. However, when linking a concept to a word as its “name,” one must remember that historical changes in traditions, customs, and everyday life affect the use of certain words, their lexical meanings, and the sense an ethnic group attaches to a word. Consequently, such shifts lead to transformations in the internal nature of the concept itself.

A concept has numerous linguistic means of fixation — so-called *means of objectivization*. Language, as is known, exists in two forms. Firstly, it represents a system of words along with the rules for their use. Secondly, it functions in speech activity, where words are actualized in utterances [4, p. 24]. Therefore, we may say that the concept is expressed both at the language level and in the sphere of speech activity.

CONCLUSION

Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin clearly defined a system of means of objectivization of a concept, which we adhere to in our research: ready-made lexemes, sememes or separate semes of various levels; paremias; free word combinations; structural and positional sentence patterns carrying typical propositions; texts and sets of texts (abstract or individual-authorial concepts) [6, p. 16].

Thus, a *concept* can be defined as a global, cognitive, and multi-component unit with a complex structure. Unlike the word, it depends on nationality, culture,

experience, and psychological traits of an individual. It should be noted that understanding the concept and meaning as distinct units remains a relevant issue in modern linguistics.

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